

ISSN 2249 - 8893

Annals of Multi-Disciplinary Research

A Quarterly International Refereed Research Journal

Volume VI

Issue 3

September 2016

Editor

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Microbial Biomass an Important Indicator of Soil Fertility: An Article

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Soil microbial biomass is the living portion of the soil organic matter excluding plant roots and soil animals larger than $5 \times 10^{-3} \mu\text{m}$. The soil microbial biomass (SMB) only comprises 1-5% of soil organic matter. The biomass is both a source and sink of the nutrients C, N, P and S contained in the organic matter. It is the center of the majority of biological activity in soil. Microbial biomass has been measured in soil by most commonly used classical technique i.e. chloroform fumigation method. The size of the SMB has been used to study soil problems relating the degradation, stabilization, effect of climatic variation and incorporation of plant C and N into the biomass etc. The nutrient availability and productivity of agro ecosystems mainly depend on the size and activity of the microbial biomass. In this way, microbial biomass is a much more sensitive indicator of changing soil conditions than the total organic matter content.

Keywords: Soil microbial biomass, soil organic matter, nutrient cycling, indicator, fumigation.

Introduction : Soil micro-organisms play a key role in nutrient cycling in the soil. Microbial processes are an integral part of the functions of ecosystems connected with fertilization and organic matter transformation and cycling of nutrients. (Pietikäinen and Fritze, 1995; Neary et al., 1999; Thirukkumaran and Parkinson, 2000). The soil microbial biomass constitutes a transformation matrix for all natural organic materials in the soil and acts as a labile reservoir of plant available nutrients (Jenkinson and Ladd, 1981). Microbial biomass, abundance and diversity have been used as indicators of soil health. It is also frequently used as an early indicator of changes in soil chemical and physical properties resulting from soil management and environmental stresses in agricultural ecosystems (Brookes, 1995; Jordan et al., 1995; Trasar-Cepeda et al., 1998; Moore et al, 2000). García-Gil et al., (2000) reported that microbial biomass is a much more sensitive indicator of changing soil conditions than the total organic matter content. Since it constitutes a significant part of the potentially mineralizable C, N and serves both as the transformation agent and source-sink of C and N (Bonde et al., 1988) and it plays an important role in C and N cycling due to rapid turnover rate. Although the soil microbial biomass C (MBC) constitutes only 1–3% of total soil C and the biomass N (MBN) up to 5% of total soil N, they are the most labile C and N pools in soils (Jenkinson and Ladd, 1981). Therefore, nutrient availability and productivity of agro ecosystems mainly depend on the size and activity of the microbial biomass (Friedel et al, 1996). The turnover time for N immobilized in the microbial biomass was found to be about ten times faster than that derived from plant material (Smith and Paul, 1990). The determination of MBN is, therefore, important for the quantification of N dynamics in agricultural ecosystems because it controls soil inorganic N availability and loss, especially in high input systems. Human activities that minimize the organic matter content of the soil may reduce enzyme activities and could alter the availability of nutrients for plant uptake (Dick et al, 1992). Therefore, the study of soil microbial biomass and their potential activity is

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important for understanding early changes in biological quality of soil following changes in the land management.

Soil microbial biomass and soil organic matter : Since microorganisms are mostly confined to the surface soil layer owing to better aeration and greater nutrient availability, microbial biomass, and various enzyme activities were significantly greater in the surface soil layer (0–10 cm) compared to the sub-surface (10–20 cm) soil layer where the organic matter content and nutrient availability was low and aeration was poor. Thus the activity of soil microbes and accumulation of N in microbial biomass seem to have been influenced by a variety of physical characteristics of soil such as soil moisture content and water holding capacity (WHC) and chemical properties such as organic matter and CEC.

Many studies (Anderson and Domsch, 1989; Ross and Tate, 1993) reported that microbial biomass and microbial activity are closely related with the content of organic matter that is positively influenced by organic matters such as post-harvest residues and organic manure. Microbial biomass is in positive correlation with the amount of organic matters supplied in a longer period, but it also responds to a single application of organic matter (Ocio et al, 1991). If only nitrogen fertilizers are applied, the rate of organic matter mineralization increases, leading to a decrease in the content of easily decomposable organic matter in the soil that is related with a decrease in microbial biomass content (Collins et al, 1992; Lovell et al, 1995).

Soil microbial biomass carbon and nitrogen as affected by cropping systems, the ratio of MBC: MBN is often used to describe the structure and the state of the microbial community. A high MBC : MBN ratio indicates that the microbial biomass contains a higher proportion of fungi, whereas a low value suggests that bacteria predominate in the microbial population (Campbell et al, 1991). The MBC: MBN ratios of selected microbial isolates extracted from soils or obtained from culture collections, and cultivated under optimal conditions, range from 7 to 12 in fungi and from 3 to 6 in bacteria (Jenkinson, 1976; Anderson and Domsch, 1989). Differences in these ratios are expected between microbial populations cultivated under laboratory conditions and those grown under natural conditions (Joergensen, 1995). Joergensen (1995) reported C : N ratios of the microbial biomass varying from 5.2 in an arable soil to 20.8 in a forest soil, with an average of 6.8 for 82 soils.

Soil organic carbon (SOC) levels are a function of inputs, dominated by plant litter contributions and rhizo deposition, and losses such as leaching, erosion and heterotrophic respiration. Therefore, changes in biomass inputs, or organic matter accumulation, will most likely also alter SOC levels in soils. Although the soil microbial biomass (SMB) only comprises 1-5% of soil organic matter (SOM) (Sparling, 1992), it is critical in organic matter decomposition and can provide an early indicator of SOM dynamics as a whole due to its faster turnover time, and hence, can be used to determine soil C dynamics under changing environmental conditions. The MBC generally comprised 1-4% of SOC. The MBC and the MBC/SOC, ratio are useful measures to monitor soil organic matter and both provide a more sensitive index than SOC measured alone (Mabuhay et al, 2006). The living fraction of organic matter, the microbial biomass, rather than total amounts of organic C, has been suggested as a useful and more sensitive measure of a change in organic matter status (Powlson and Jenkinson, 1981; Powlson et al, 1987; Cerny et al, 2003).

Method for the measurement of soil microbial biomass : Soil microbial biomass C and N were determined using the fumigation-extraction procedures proposed by Vance et al. (1987) and Brookes et al. (1985), respectively. Organic C was determined by dichromate digestion and back-titration with ferrous ammonium sulphate (Vance et al., 1987).

The soil MBC : A portion of soil sample (10 g) was fumigated using ethanol- free chloroform (25 ml) placed in a vacuum desiccators containing 10 g soda lime (Joergensen, 1995). The chloroform was allowed to boil under reduced pressure for 2 min followed by incubation at 25°C for 24 h. The fumigated soil and another portion of the same soil sample (10 g, unfumigated) were separately extracted with 40 ml of 0.5 (M) K₂SO₄ for 30 min in an oscillating shaker at 200 rpm. An aliquot of the filtered extract (8 ml) was refluxed with 0.4 (N) ferrous ammonium sulfate using ferroin indicators (Vance et al, 1987; Wu et al, 1990; Mueller et al 1992).

Soil Microbial Biomass carbon (MBC) was determined as follows:

$$\text{Extracted org-C} = \frac{(H-S) \times M \times D \times E \times 1000}{C \times A} \\ \times \frac{K}{W \times d_{wt}} \text{ (}\mu\text{g g}^{-1} \text{ dry soil)}$$

Where H= titration solution consumed by the hot (refluxed) blank (ml), S= titration solution consumed by the sample (ml), C= titration solution consumed by the cold (unrefluxed) blank (ml), M= normality of the K₂Cr₂O₇ solution, D= volume of K₂Cr₂O₇ solution added to the reaction mixture (ml), A= aliquot of the extract (8 ml), E=3 (conversion of Cr^{VI+} to Cr^{III+}), K= volume of the extractant (ml) and d_{wt}= dry weight of moist soil per gram.

$$\text{Soil MBC (}\mu\text{g g}^{-1} \text{ dry soil)} = \frac{Ec}{KEc} = \frac{Ec}{0.38}$$

Where Ec = (extracted organic-C from fumigated sample)-(extracted organic-C from unfumigated sample) and K_{Ec}= calibration factor.

The Soil MBN : Microbial biomass nitrogen was determined by a fumigation-extraction method (Brookes et al, 1985). After pre-extraction a half of the samples was extracted with 100 ml of 0.5M K₂SO₄ for 45-minute shaking of samples was followed by centrifugation. The content of total extractable nitrogen was determined in the extraction. The other half of the samples was chloroform fumigated. Samples were put into desiccators where a dish with 30 ml chloroform CHCl₃ was placed. A vacuum pump was used to induce vacuum until chloroform started boiling. Fumigation took place in darkness, at 25°C for 24 hours. Similarly like chloroform-untreated samples, fumigated samples were extracted with 100 ml of 0.5M K₂SO₄. The content of total extractable nitrogen was measured in the extraction after centrifugation. Microbial biomass N was calculated as a difference in N content in fumigated and nonfumigated sample (E_N) using coefficient k_{EN} (microbial biomass N = E_N /k_{EN}). The coefficient k_{EN} indicates an extractable portion of microbial biomass after fumigation. The value k_{EN} = 0.54 was used to calculate microbial biomass N (Brookes et al, 1985; Joergensen and Mueller, 1996).

Conclusion : These interesting reports for microbial biomass invoke great expectation for further research on effect on microbial biomass due to various parameters affecting the soil like use of pesticides, fertilizers, green manure, land use etc. However, further in depth studies would be more realistic approach before arriving at a general conclusion for the prediction of soil fertility.

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